

Science technology & Digital finance

journal homepage: <https://supportresult.uz/index.php/stdf>**BANK RESOURCES IN THE MODERNIZATION OF THE ECONOMY****¹Tuychieva Nodira, ²Saitov Sirojiddin**¹Assistant of the Jizzakh branch of the National University of Uzbekistan named after Mirzo Ulugbek.²Senior lecturer of Jizzakh branch of the National University of Uzbekistan named after Mirzo Ulugbek.**БАНКОВСКИЕ РЕСУРСЫ В МОДЕРНИЗАЦИИ ЭКОНОМИКИ****¹Туйчиева Нодира, ²Сайтов Сирожиддин**¹Ассистент Джизакского филиала Национального университета Узбекистана имени Мирзо Улугбека.²Старший преподаватель Джизакского филиала Национального университета Узбекистана имени Мирзо Улугбека.**IQTISODIYOTNI MODERNIZATSIYA QILISHDA BANK RESURSLARI****¹Tuychieva Nodira, ²Saitov Sirojiddin**¹Mirzo Ulug'bek nomidagi O'zbekiston Milliy universitetining Jizzax filiali assistenti.²Mirzo Ulug'bek nomidagi O'zbekiston Milliy universitetining Jizzax filiali katta o'qituvchisi.**abstract**

Banks play an important role in the financial system and economy. They are it has the characteristic of providing the economy and, if necessary, developing it. It is worth mentioning that banking activity requires sufficient bank resources. Bank perfect organization and efficient use of resources which serves as the basis for the efficient operation of banks. In the article, the author discusses the same issues: the importance of commercial banks, resources and he thinks in detail about the effective use of these resources.

аннотация

Банки играют важную роль в финансовой системе и экономике. Они заключаются в том, что оно обладает свойством обеспечивать экономику и, при необходимости, развивать ее. Стоит отметить, что банковская деятельность требует достаточных банковских ресурсов. Совершенная организация банка и эффективное использование ресурсов, которые служат основой для эффективной работы банков. В статье автор обсуждает те же вопросы: важность коммерческих банков, ресурсов, и он подробно размышляет об эффективном использовании этих ресурсов.

annotatsiya

Banklar moliya tizimi va iqtisodiyotida muhim rol o'ynaydi. Ular iqtisodiyotni ta'minlash va kerak bo'lganda uni rivojlantirish xususiyatiga ega. Ta'kidlash joizki, bank faoliyati etarli bank resurslarini talab qiladi. Bank mukammal tashkil etish va resurslardan samarali foydalanish bu banklarning samarali ishlashi uchun asos bo'lib xizmat qiladi. Maqolada muallif xuddi shu masalalarni muhokama qiladi: tijorat banklarining ahamiyati, resurslari va u ushbu resurslardan samarali foydalanish haqida batafsil o'ylaydi.

Keywords:

Banks, bank resources, credit resources, bank funds, involved funds, deposits, interbank loans, term deposits, bank balance and etc.

Ключевые слова:

банки, банковские ресурсы, кредитные ресурсы, банковские средства, привлеченные средства, депозиты, межбанковские кредиты, срочные депозиты, банковский баланс и т.д.

Kalit so'zlar:

banklar, bank resurslari, kredit resurslari, bank mablag'lari, jalb qilingan mablag'lar, depozitlar,

banklararo kreditlar, muddatli depozitlar, bank balans va boshqalar.

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Introduction

As the main component of the financial system, banks owe money to depositors efficiently allocate funds to recipients. They provide financial services, which costs information about savings and borrowing opportunities reduces. These financial services make the overall economy more efficient helps to do. This is not just an academic exercise; many former eastern blocking countries to create financial markets and market oriented faced with this question when starting to develop banks and other financial institutions they started coming. Banks work by borrowing money: usually, by accepting deposits or borrowing money markets. Banks are physical surplus from individuals, businesses, financial institutions and governments takes a loan with his funds (savings).

Then they are deposits and loans lending or securities from funds (liabilities of the bank), (bank assets) they use to buy. Banks are business loans entities, other financial institutions, individuals and governments (when funds are needed for investments or other purposes) they give. Interest rates provide price signals for borrowers, lenders and banks. The banking system takes deposits, makes loans, and responds to interest rate signals help to efficiently channel funds from savers to borrowers will give.

Banks also credit card in the amount of \$100 or billion dollar corporate merger financing to a large corporation serves a wide range of borrowers. This shows that the main part of banks' sources of funds are deposits - checks, savings, money market are deposit accounts and time certificates. Most of these funds the most commonly used purpose is real estate, commercial and industrial lending. Asset and liability composition of individual banks differs from industry indicators possible because some institutions have specialized or limited banking services they show.

Discussion and results

In the conditions of the market economy, the economic resources of commercial banks are created is important in the rational implementation of activities. Resource base attracting new customers in the formation is a component of the resource base. Resource is derived from the French word "Resource", which means funds, means opportunity, reserve, source of income, raw material, etc.

Economical sources, the word "resource" often appears in different meanings. Russian scientist O.Lavrushin, the resources of commercial banks or "banks resources"

is the sum of the bank's own and attracted resources at its disposal is used in the implementation of its asset operations. For example: natural resources, financial resources, economic resources, human resources, etc. Based on this, economic resources are the main economic opportunities can be considered as one of the elements. It is all about the development of society distributed in stages.

The resource is a clear economic and social development used to achieve their goals. Most of the economic resources are this are financial resources, which are money and tax resources, and economic serves to support development. The main financial resources sources are temporary free funds, taxes, individuals funds, funds related to issuing check deposits, considering bank resources, which are an integral part of financial resources we go out Initially, the obligations of banks and their resources are the that they are not concepts. Bank liabilities of bank resources is the source. Therefore, Bank resources are reflected in the passive part of the bank balance will be delivered. Their size depends on:

- banking activities carried out at the expense of own funds;
- Monetary policy of the Central Bank and loan funds from banks and their structure;
- the amount of compulsory reserve of a commercial bank in the Central Bank;
- other liabilities; In economic sources and studies on the formation of bank funds you can find different interpretations. Including "Bank resources", "credit resources", "deposit resources", "Bank liabilities" and other concepts possible According to the Russian scientist Lavrushin, the resources of commercial banks or "Bank resources" are the sum of own and borrowed resources, in a bank the asset is used to conduct transactions. The need for bank resources appears in the formation of banks and implementation of banking activities. Banks should have their own capital in the early stages of bank formation and it is necessary to attract resources for its future activities.

The bank's own funds are the authorized capital of the bank and its equivalent funds, including reserve capital, special funds, material incentive fund, various other organized funds and retained earnings. Attractive funds - deposits, savings, borrowed funds reflected in current and correspondent account sheets. Trade banks, like other economic entities, a certain amount of money funds, that is, resources to support commercial and economic activities must be. In addition, the scale of active operations with the size of resources dependent. Such a situation of attracting resources is the emergence of competition between banks causes to be. Based on this, banking resources are the activities of commercial banks serve as the basis for the reserve and profit for the bank is a possibility. One of the main tasks of the bank is to attract more free money to make and earn income by investing them in other eligible assets is to

direct. Bank resources with the help of passive operations of banks is created and studied partially by dividing into two large groups. Bank balance liabilities are: own funds and borrowed funds. Bank the main part of its resources is the funds of bank clients. Commerce dividing the resource base of banks into the following groups by resource types possible: These are own funds, borrowed funds and bank loans.

Asset and liability management is important for a bank is one of the tasks. By attracting funds or placing them both related operations are important in the activity of banks. Their effective organization allows to achieve high results in banks' activities will give. The bank's resources are formed through its passive operations. Therefore, the bank formation of resources, its passive account numbers or active-passive account operations related to the increase of funds in the numbers of banks called passive operations. In the management of financial resources of commercial banks the main attention is paid to the sources of funds in the liabilities of the bank balance. This funds are divided into two large groups - liabilities and capital. Obligations - at the expense of the funds attracted by the bank, and the capital is the bank's own formed at the expense of funds. Stable sources of these funds formation due to efficient operation of commercial banks and economically provides strength. Stages of circulation of bank resources:

1. Funds.
2. Allocation of credit.
3. Loan and interest payment.

Regulation of the resource base of commercial banks is the direct responsibility of the central bank is not a task, but within the framework of the monetary policy of the National Bank of the Republic of Belarus by applying various methods of monetary policy, directly or commercially indirectly affects the amount of bank resources. On the whole, order a The National Bank of the Republic of Belarus is a resource of commercial banks with requirements to ensure the safety and liquidity of the entire banking system dependent. The purpose of passive operations by commercial banks:

- providing banking activities with resources;
- additional funds that can be directed to the economy
- formation of sources; residents and legal entities by paying bank interest on the funds involved
- increase the income of individuals; increase the size of own capital;
- organization of reserve funds to protect banking operations from riskto do

An important place among the bank's liabilities is occupied by the bank's own capital. Banks also forms its own capital in the process of its establishment. Bank capital is an important basis for ensuring bank stability. Own for the bank funds are a

source of financial resources. Bank and its activities the factor of ensuring its stability is the bank's authorized capital, and at the same time the bank the composition of resources is important.

This is before the initial costs of the bank (in its activities (for example, acquisition of land, installation of equipment, payment of wages to employees and others) is very important in implementation. In the next stages, the bank's own capital plays an important role in expanding bank operations. Bank capital another important feature is the guarantee of protection. Bank unexpected covers losses and additional costs with its own capital. The bank's own funds include bank capital. Bank capital is the founders of the bank funds deposited by consists of retained earnings. But it should be noted that bank capital is a bank are the accumulated funds of the founders, various reserves and retained earnings ensures expansion of bank capital. Commercial since October 1, 2017. The minimum amount of authorized capital of banks is 100.0 bln. should amount to soums. The operating commercial banks are chartered until January 1, 2019 they should bring their capital to this amount.

The bank's own resources are bank capital and equivalent items represents The role and size of the authorized capital is a characteristic of commercial banks it differs from enterprises and organizations engaged in other activities, because banks cover less than 10 percent of the total need for funds from their own funds. Equity and debt for state-owned banks determines the minimum limit of the ratio between funds. The bank's own resources are a necessary condition for its stability in the financial market. The beginning of the establishment of a bank At the stage, own funds cover priority expenses, without which the bank would not be able to operate cannot start. In the future, banks will have to reduce their own resources create reserves that are credit risk and their resources to long-term assets is the main source of investments. Share of the bank's own funds from 12% to 20% of their liabilities. To manage resources and commercial banks special attention should be paid to fundraising activities, which directly related to the placement of the size and corresponding structure of the sources determination. The most important task when banks use their own and loan funds is at the same time in itself the maximum profitability of bank assets and the optimal level of liquidity is to provide.

Conclusion

In conclusion, it can be said that the main volume of income is credit to banks from investments, investments in securities and investments is provided; The total liquidity of the bank resources to highly liquid assets provided by placement: in the central bank and other commercial banks in correspondent accounts. A certain part of the resources are banks is spent on the purchase of fixed assets and intangible assets.

Such assets are described as illiquid and non-yielding, but they are different necessary to ensure the normal operation of the bank, as well as business entities.

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